

Linear Plasmids in *Micrococcus*: Insights into a Common Ancestor and Transfer by Conjugation

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table S1. Primers and PCR conditions.

Primer	Sequence	Annealing	Extension
pA1_2_F	5'-GATCGGTCGACGTGGACTTC-3'	69 °C	60 s
pA1_2_R	5'-CCGGTGATGTCGTCAG-3'		
d19560_1	5'-GTAAAACGACGGCCAGTGCCAC GATCATCGCGCTGGACTTC-3'	72 °C	90 s
dComEA-sGFPml_1	5'-ATTCGCTGACCGCGTGAGAC-3'		
kan_R3	5'-GAGTCCCGCTCAGAAGAACTC-3'		
dOleH-1	5'-CGAAGATGGTGTGCGGGTAG-3'	72 °C	90 s
dOleH-4	5'-TCGGACATCCTGGCCAATGC-3'		
pA1_G_1_Mut	5'-TGGACGCGCATGGAATCCAC-3'	62 °C	30 s
pA1_G_2_Mut	5'-CGCATGAACTGCTGAC-3'		
pA1_G_3_Mut	5'-GCTGTGCTGGCTTC-3'	65 °C	30 s
pA1_G_4_Mut	5'-ATACCTCGTGCAGTCTTACC-3'		
hygBF1	5'-GGCACCTATCTCAGCGATCTGTC-3'	70 °C	45 s
hygBR1	5'-CGGGCGGCCCCGGGCGTCAGG-3'		
d15kb-check-F	5'-AGCGTTCAGCTGCGACGATG-3'	70 °C	150 s
d15kb-check-R	5'-ATAAGGCCCTCGCGTGACTG-3'		

PCR concentrations

5X Q5 Reaction Buffer	5 µL
Primer forward (10 µM)	1.25 µL
Primer reverse (10 µM)	1.25 µL
dNTPs (10 mM)	0.5 µL
Q5 High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase (New England Biolabs)	0.25 µL
5X Q5 High GC Enhancer	5 µL
Template	5 ng (Plasmid) or 50 ng (DNA Genomic)
Nuclease-Free Water	to 25 µL

PCR procedure

	Temperature	Time	
Initial denaturation	98 °C	30 s	
Denaturation	98 °C	10 s	
Annealing	See above	30 s	30 cycles
Extension	72 °C	See above	
Final extension	72 °C	2 min	
Preservation	4 °C	∞	

Supplementary Table S2. Sequence features of the plasmids analyzed.

Plasmid	Length (bp)	GC content (%)	ORFs total	ORFs with known function
pLMA1	109,112	68.40	125	62
pLMA7	82,075	69.56	93	33
pLMV7	92,815	69.40	114	28
pJD12	75,989	68.86	80	27

Supplementary Table S3. Function assigned to each ORF in pLMA1.

ORF	Start	End	Length (nt)	Strain	Protein / Function	Conserved region
pLMA1						
1	60	740	680	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
2	997	1560	563	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
3	1545	2324	779	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
4	2222	2965	743	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
5	2975	3985	1010	-	<i>IS481 family transposase</i>	
6	4350	4451	101	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
7	4661	4990	329	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
8	5151	5420	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
9	5500	5769	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
10	5798	6349	551	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
11	6773	8434	1661	-	<i>Putative transposase</i>	1
12	8517	9254	737	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
13	9251	9700	449	-	<i>Helix-turn-helix transcriptional regulator</i>	
14	9704	10003	299	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
15	10314	10490	176	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
16	10628	10984	356	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
17	10905	11774	869	-	<i>IS21 putative ATP-binding protein IstB</i>	
18	11842	12627	785	-	<i>IS21-like element helper ATPase IstB</i>	
19	12624	14147	1523	-	<i>IS21 family transposase</i>	
20	14933	15133	200	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
21	15275	15592	317	-	<i>Integrase core domain-containing protein</i>	
22	15573	17015	1442	-	<i>Transposase InsF for insertion sequence IS3</i>	
23	16981	17691	710	-	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>	
24	17688	18017	329	-	<i>Transposase</i>	
25	18211	18345	134	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
26	18452	18784	332	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
27	18881	19546	665	-	<i>HNH endonuclease</i>	2
28	19710	21884	2174	+	<i>Site-specific DNA-methyltransferase</i>	
29	21890	24475	2585	+	<i>Type III restriction enzyme, res subunit</i>	

30	24562	24879	317	-	<i>Resolvase, N-terminal domain protein</i>	
31	25999	26475	476	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
32	26594	26749	155	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
33	27071	27697	626	+	<i>Transposon Tn21 resolvase</i>	
34	27824	28393	569	-	<i>Recombinase family protein</i>	
35	28694	29200	506	+	<i>Universal stress protein</i>	
36	29197	29943	746	+	<i>2,3-diphosphoglycerate-dependent phosphoglycerate mutase</i>	
37	29940	30443	503	+	<i>Putative fluoride ion transporter CrcB 1</i>	
38	30440	30811	371	+	<i>CrcB family protein</i>	
39	30859	31344	485	+	<i>Inorganic diphosphatase</i>	
40	31487	32821	1334	+	<i>Phosphopyruvate hydratase</i>	
41	32806	33732	926	-	<i>LysR family transcriptional regulator</i>	
42	33803	34960	1157	+	<i>Tellurite-Resistance/Dicarboxylate Transporter (TDT) family</i>	
43	34957	35541	584	+	<i>Uracil-DNA glycosylase</i>	
44	35682	36284	602	+	<i>Transposase for transposon Tn552</i>	
45	36291	37685	1394	+	<i>DDE-type integrase/transposase/recombinase</i>	
46	37682	38494	812	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
47	38686	39216	530	+	<i>TetR family transcriptional regulator</i>	
48	39213	39557	344	+	<i>Multidrug resistance protein, SMR family</i>	
49	39557	39886	329	+	<i>QacE family quaternary ammonium compound efflux SMR transporter</i>	
50	40023	41078	1055	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
51	41199	41471	272	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	3
52	41468	42181	713	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
53	42191	42652	461	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	4
54	42643	43422	779	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
55	43415	45184	1769	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
56	45339	45953	614	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
57	45997	46584	587	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
58	46574	47344	770	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
59	47439	47993	554	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	5
60	47998	48633	635	-	<i>Prepilin peptidase</i>	
61	48614	52075	3461	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
62	52170	53222	1052	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
63	53621	53788	167	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
64	53952	54890	938	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
65	54884	55585	701	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
66	55601	56017	416	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
67	56020	56469	449	-	<i>Pilus assembly protein</i>	
68	56466	56876	410	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
69	56920	57102	182	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
70	57202	58074	872	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
71	58071	58937	866	-	<i>Type II secretion system F family protein</i>	

72	58934	59800	866	-	<i>Pilus assembly protein, ATPase of CpaF family</i>
73	60515	61339	824	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
74	61336	62013	677	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
75	62185	62481	296	+	<i>MarR family transcriptional regulator</i>
76	62666	63589	923	+	<i>ParA family protein</i>
77	64112	65263	1151	-	<i>Plasmid encoded RepA protein</i>
78	65572	66378	806	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
79	66641	66868	227	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
80	66865	67959	1094	+	<i>Conjugal transfer protein</i>
81	67986	68255	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
82	68273	68788	515	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
83	68785	71340	2555	+	<i>IV secretion system protein VirB4</i>
84	71337	73283	1946	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
85	73280	75046	1766	+	<i>Peptidoglycan DD-metalloendopeptidase family protein</i>
86	75043	75828	785	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
87	76145	76291	146	-	<i>Fluoroacetate dehalogenase</i>
88	76563	77429	866	+	<i>Alpha/beta hydrolase</i>
89	77489	77935	446	-	<i>IS5 family transposase</i>
90	78018	78368	350	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
91	78704	79042	338	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
92	79320	79460	140	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
93	79692	80405	713	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
94	80434	80679	245	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
95	81250	81948	698	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
96	82284	83057	773	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
97	83556	84032	476	+	<i>ADP-ribose pyrophosphatase</i>
98	84160	84591	431	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
99	84617	85237	620	-	<i>SAM-dependent methyltransferase</i>
100	85332	85901	569	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
101	86064	86591	527	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
102	86727	87620	893	-	<i>LysR family transcriptional regulator</i>
103	87700	88599	899	+	<i>EamA family transporter</i>
104	88596	89060	464	+	<i>Transposase for insertion sequence element IS1081</i>
105	89171	90415	1244	+	<i>IS256 family transposase</i>
106	90421	90672	251	+	<i>NAD dependent epimerase/dehydratase family protein</i>
107	90759	91745	986	+	<i>IS481 family transposase</i>
108	91932	92225	293	+	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>
109	92225	93106	881	+	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>
110	93411	94229	818	+	<i>23S ribosomal RNA methyltransferase Erm</i>
111	94872	95201	329	+	<i>Transposase for insertion sequence element IS904</i>
112	95198	96121	923	+	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>
113	96095	96622	527	-	<i>DMT family transporter</i>
114	96762	98174	1412	+	<i>Transcriptional regulator, GntR</i>

					<i>family</i>
115	98224	98400	176	-	<i>Putative short-chain type dehydrogenase/reductase VdlC</i>
116	98518	99348	830	-	<i>SDR family NAD(P)-dependent oxidoreductase</i>
117	99402	99929	527	+	<i>TetR family transcriptional regulator</i>
118	100166	100741	575	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
119	100998	101771	773	-	<i>Prolyl oligopeptidase family protein</i>
120	102668	104869	2201	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
121	104871	105176	305	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
122	105280	106623	1343	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
123	106657	107052	395	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
124	107256	107486	230	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>
125	107889	108845	956	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>

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Supplementary Table S4. Function assigned to each ORF in pJD12.

ORF	Start	End	Length (nt)	Strain	Protein / Function	Conserved region
pJD12						
1	277	624	347	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
2	1048	2709	1661	-	<i>Transposase</i>	
3	2792	3529	737	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
4	3526	3975	449	-	<i>Helix-turn-helix transcriptional regulator</i>	
5	3979	4278	299	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
6	4590	4766	176	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
7	4919	5179	260	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
8	5176	5556	380	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
9	6055	6372	317	+	<i>Transposase</i>	
10	6375	7076	701	+	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>	
11	7042	8484	1442	+	<i>IS30 family transposase</i>	
12	8838	9908	1070	+	<i>IS110 family transposase</i>	
13	10242	10424	182	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
14	10425	10649	224	+	<i>Bacterial regulatory protein, arsR family</i>	
15	10649	11581	932	+	<i>Co/Zn/Cd efflux system component protein</i>	
16	11553	11804	251	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
17	12163	12828	665	-	<i>HNH endonuclease</i>	2
18	12992	15145	2153	+	<i>Site-specific DNA-methyltransferase</i>	
19	15151	17736	2585	+	<i>Type III restriction enzyme, res subunit</i>	
20	17873	18163	290	-	<i>Transposase</i>	
21	18205	19080	875	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
22	19282	19542	260	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
23	20709	21950	1241	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
24	22289	22645	356	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
25	22656	23225	569	-	<i>Site-specific DNA recombinase</i>	

26	23505	24971	1466	+	<i>MFS transporter</i>	
27	24989	25558	569	+	<i>Transcriptional regulator, TetR family</i>	
28	25764	26444	680	-	<i>Iron (metal) dependent repressor, DtxR family</i>	
29	26461	27735	1274	-	<i>Mn²⁺ and Fe²⁺ transporters of the NRAMP family</i>	
30	27926	28522	596	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
31	28660	28932	272	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	3
32	28929	29645	716	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
33	29656	30123	467	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	4
34	30114	30893	779	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
35	30886	32655	1769	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
36	32810	33424	614	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
37	33468	34055	587	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
38	34058	34933	875	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
39	35030	35584	554	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
40	35589	36224	635	-	<i>Prepilin peptidase</i>	
41	36205	39672	3467	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
42	39768	41030	1262	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
43	41219	41461	242	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
44	41550	42488	938	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
45	42482	43183	701	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
46	43199	43615	416	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
47	43618	44067	449	-	<i>Pilus assembly protein</i>	
48	44064	44474	410	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
49	44519	44701	182	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
50	44801	45673	872	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
51	45683	46537	854	-	<i>Type II secretion system F family protein</i>	
52	46534	48117	1583	-	<i>Pilus assembly protein, ATPase of CpaF family</i>	
53	48114	48938	824	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	5
54	48935	49639	704	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
55	49811	50080	269	+	<i>MarR family transcriptional regulator</i>	
56	50265	51188	923	+	<i>ParA family protein</i>	
57	51190	51816	626	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
58	51869	52888	1019	-	<i>Plasmid encoded RepA protein</i>	
59	52857	53132	275	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
60	53173	53979	806	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
61	54242	54469	227	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
62	54466	55560	1094	+	<i>Conjugal transfer protein</i>	
63	55592	55885	293	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
64	55903	56418	515	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
65	56415	58970	2555	+	<i>IV secretion system protein VirB4</i>	
66	58967	60913	1946	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
67	60910	62676	1766	+	<i>Peptidoglycan DD-metalloendopeptidase family protein</i>	

68	62673	63458	785	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
69	64012	64545	533	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
70	64835	65536	701	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
71	66177	68390	2213	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	6
72	68392	68697	305	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
73	68801	70117	1316	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
74	70151	70546	395	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
75	70750	70980	230	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
76	71322	72353	1031	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
77	72502	72741	239	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
78	72956	73342	386	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
79	73975	74802	827	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
80	74646	75425	779	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	

Supplementary Table S5. Function assigned to each ORF in pLMA7.

ORF	Start	End	Length (nt)	Strain	Protein / Function	Conserved region
pLMA7						
1	41	211	170	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
2	366	1343	977	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
3	1540	1797	257	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
4	1761	2057	296	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
5	2094	2774	680	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
6	2994	3479	485	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
7	3748	4461	713	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
8	4725	4916	191	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
9	5033	5683	650	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
10	5935	6600	665	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
11	6813	7142	329	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
12	7303	7572	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
13	7652	7921	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
14	7951	8502	551	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
15	9108	10769	1661	-	<i>Transposase</i>	1
16	10852	11589	737	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
17	11586	12035	449	-	<i>Helix-turn-helix transcriptional regulator</i>	
18	12039	12338	299	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
19	12648	12824	176	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
20	12968	13237	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
21	13234	13413	179	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
22	14147	14812	665	-	<i>HNH endonuclease</i>	2
23	14976	15362	386	+	<i>Site-specific DNA-methyltransferase (type III restriction-modification system methylation subunit)</i>	
24	15387	16301	914	-	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>	
25	16298	16618	320	-	<i>Transposase</i>	

26	16744	16959	215	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
27	16927	17151	224	+	<i>Regulatory protein ArsR</i>	
28	17151	18083	932	+	<i>Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance protein CzcD</i>	
29	18157	18306	149	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
30	18341	18538	197	+	<i>Transposase</i>	
31	18748	21225	2477	-	<i>S8 family serine peptidase</i>	
32	21261	22238	977	-	<i>ATP-binding protein</i>	
33	22388	22513	125	+	<i>Transposase</i>	
34	22988	23542	554	-	<i>Recombinase family protein</i>	
35	23725	24405	680	-	<i>Mn-dependent transcriptional regulator MntR</i>	
36	24422	25696	1274	-	<i>Manganese transport protein MntH</i>	
37	25887	26483	596	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
38	26776	28242	1466	+	<i>MFS transporter</i>	
39	28260	28829	569	+	<i>Transcriptional regulator, TetR family</i>	
40	29001	29273	272	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	3
41	29270	29983	713	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
42	29993	30454	461	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	4
43	30445	31224	779	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
44	31217	32986	1769	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
45	33032	33235	203	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
46	33225	34073	848	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
47	34170	34724	554	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	5
48	34729	35364	635	-	<i>Prepilin peptidase</i>	
49	35345	38818	3473	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
50	38913	40040	1127	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
51	40364	40531	167	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
52	40695	41633	938	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
53	41627	42328	701	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
54	42344	42760	416	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
55	42763	43212	449	-	<i>Pilus assembly protein</i>	
56	43209	43619	410	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
57	43664	43846	182	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
58	43946	44818	872	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
59	44815	45681	866	-	<i>Type II secretion system F family protein</i>	
60	45678	47261	1583	-	<i>Pilus assembly protein, ATPase of CpaF family</i>	
61	47258	48082	824	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
62	48079	48756	677	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
63	48928	49224	296	+	<i>MarR family transcriptional regulator</i>	
64	49409	50332	923	+	<i>ParA family protein</i>	
65	50334	50960	626	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
66	50979	51980	1001	-	<i>Plasmid encoded RepA protein</i>	
67	52283	53089	806	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
68	53352	53579	227	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	

69	53576	54670	1094	+	<i>Conjugal transfer protein</i>	
70	54697	54966	269	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
71	54984	55499	515	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
72	55496	58051	2555	+	<i>IV secretion system protein VirB4</i>	
73	58048	59994	1946	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
74	59991	61757	1766	+	<i>Peptidoglycan DD-metalloendopeptidase family protein</i>	
75	62089	62538	449	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
76	63205	63831	626	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
77	64200	65207	1007	-	<i>IS481 family transposase</i>	
78	65445	65747	302	+	<i>Transposase</i>	
79	65744	66619	875	+	<i>IS3 family transposase</i>	6
80	66962	68614	1652	+	<i>Putative ABC transporter permease protein</i>	
81	68611	69843	1232	+	<i>Tetracycline-resistance determinant TetV</i>	
82	70656	72869	2213	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
83	72871	73176	305	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
84	73280	74623	1343	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
85	74657	75052	395	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
86	75256	75486	230	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
87	75952	76569	617	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
88	76862	77818	956	+	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
89	77966	78205	239	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
90	78420	78767	347	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
91	78794	79804	1010	-	<i>IS481 family transposase</i>	
92	80004	80183	179	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	
93	81293	82072	779	-	<i>Hypothetical protein</i>	

Supplementary Table S6. Location of plasmid replication genes and putative iterons in pLMA1, pJD12 and pLMA7.

pLMA1					
<i>rep gen</i>		Iterons			
N° ORF	Position	N°	Length (bp)	Position	Sequence
77	64112..65263	1	29	6499..6527	5'-GGAAGCTCCGCCC G CGCAGGGATGAGCCA-3' *
		2	29	6560..6588	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		3	29	6621..6649	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		4	29	6682..6710	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		5	29	6743..6771	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
pJD12					
<i>rep gen</i>		Iterons			
N° ORF	Position	N°	Length (bp)	Position	Sequence
58	51869..52888	1	29	774..802	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCA-3' *
		2	29	835..863	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3' *
		3	29	896..924	5'-GGAGGCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		4	29	957..985	5'-GGAGGCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		5	29	1018..1046	5'-GGAGGCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
pLMA7					
<i>rep gen</i>		Iterons			
N° ORF	Position	N°	Length (bp)	Position	Sequence
66	50979..51980	1	29	8651..8679	5'-GGAAGCTCCGCCC G CGCAGGGATGAGCCA-3' *
		2	29	8712..8740	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		3	29	8773..8801	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCA-3' *
		4	29	8834..8862	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		5	29	8895..8923	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		6	29	8956..8984	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'
		7	29	9017..9045	5'-GGAAGCTCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3' *
		8	29	9078..9106	5'-GGAAGCCCCGCGCACGCAGGGATGAGCCC-3'

*Bases highlighted in bold correspond to changes from the consensus sequence

Supplementary Fig. S1. The Andean lakes are located in the northwest of Argentina. Laguna Azul and Laguna Diamante are located in the province of Catamarca, Laguna Vilama in the province of Jujuy and Laguna Huaca Huasi in the Cumbres Calchaquíes, north of the province of Tucumán. Source: Google Maps.

Supplementary Fig. S2. Sequence comparison of the linear plasmids pLMA1 (109,112 bp) and pLMA7 (82,075 bp). Homologous regions are shown in red, the different color intensities mirror different similarity values, with higher intensity corresponding to greater sequence identity. An identity greater than 89 % and a minimum of 157 base pairs were used as cut-off criteria. The conserved regions in both plasmids are plotted in blocks of different colors (1-12). Above and below the sequence of each plasmid, the GC content is plotted ranging from 45 to 89.16 % with an average of 68.40 % for pLMA1 and from 45 to 88.33 % with an average of 69.56 % for pLMA7.

Supplementary Fig. S3. Results from conjugation assay, CFU on LB plates with Km and Em. When the recipient strains TrpE16 Δ 19560:kan and TrpE16 Δ comEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan are grown together with the donor strain *Micrococcus* sp. A1 transconjugants are observed on the selective plates both in the absence and presence of DNase I. When the strains are grown separately no colonies are obtained.

Supplementary Fig. S4. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants obtained with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan, resulting in TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1, from conjugation assay with (#1A-#4A) and without (#1B-#4B) DNase I. PCR reactions on *Micrococcus* sp. A1, *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan and *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers pA1_2_F and pA1_2_R targeted against pLMA1 were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and *Micrococcus* sp. A1 is 1,617 bp. For TrpE16Δ19560 and TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S5. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants obtained with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan, resulting in TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan pLMA1, from conjugation assay with (#1A-#4A) and without (#1B-#4B) DNase I. PCR reactions on *Micrococcus* sp. A1, *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan and *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers pA1_2_F and pA1_2_R targeted against pLMA1 were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and *Micrococcus* sp. A1 is 1,617 bp. For TrpE16Δ19560 and TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S6. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants obtained with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan, resulting in TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1, from conjugation assay with (#1A-#4A) and without (#1B-#4B) DNase I. PCR reactions on *Micrococcus* sp. A1, *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan and *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomeEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers d19560_1 and kan_R3 targeted against the specific chromosomal modification at the ORF mlut_19560 of *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and TrpE16Δ19560 is 1,925 bp. For *Micrococcus* sp. A1 and TrpE16ΔcomeEA/EC no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S7. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants obtained with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan, resulting in TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan pLMA1, from conjugation assay with (#1A-#4A) and without (#1B-#4B) DNase I. PCR reactions on *Micrococcus* sp. A1, *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan and *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers dComEA-sGFPml_1 and kan_R3 targeted against the specific chromosomal modification at the *comEA/EC* locus of *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC:td-Tomato-kan were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and TrpE16ΔcomEA/EC is 3,501 bp. For *Micrococcus* sp. A1 and TrpE16Δ19560 no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S8. Results from transformation assay using isolated plasmid pJET-trpE. CFU on CAH plates. Due to conversion to prototrophy after DNA uptake transformants of *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan show growth on CAH plates. No growth is observed (except for a few spontaneous mutants) when DNase I is added or no DNA is added.

Supplementary Fig. S9. Results from transformation assay using isolated plasmid pJET-trpE. CFU on CAH plates. No growth is observed (except for a few spontaneous mutants) when pJET-trpE is added to the *M. luteus* TrpE16ΔcomEA:td-Tomato-kan strain. The deletion of *comEA/EC* genes leads to a loss of transformability and thus no transformants appear that can growth on CAH media.

Supplementary Fig. S10. Results from conjugation assay using either *Micrococcus* sp. A1 or former transconjugant *M. luteus* TrpE16 Δ 19560:kan pLMA1 as donors and *M. luteus* TrpE16 Δ ole:hyg as recipient strain. CFU on LB plates containing Hyg and Em. Colonies are observed on the selective plates when the recipient strain is grown together with the donors. No colonies are obtained when the strains are grown separately.

Supplementary Fig. S11. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants (#1-#4) obtained from conjugation assay with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16 Δ ole:hyg and *M. luteus* TrpE16 Δ 19560:kan pLMA1 as donor. PCR reactions on donor and recipient with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers pA1_2_F and pA1_2_R targeted against pLMA1 were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and TrpE16 Δ 19560:kan pLMA1 is 1,617 bp, for TrpE16 Δ ole:hyg no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S12. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants (#1-#4) obtained from conjugation assay with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16Δole:hyg and *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1 as donor. PCR reactions on donor and recipient with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers dOleH-1 and dOleH-4 targeted against a chromosomal locus specific for the recipient were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and TrpE16Δole:hyg is 3,449 bp, for TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1 7,274 bp are expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S13. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants (#1-#4) obtained from conjugation assay with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16 Δ ole:hyg and *Micrococcus* sp. A1 as donor. PCR reactions on donor and recipient with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers pA1_2_F and pA1_2_R targeted against pLMA1 were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and *Micrococcus* sp. A1 is 1,617 bp, for TrpE16 Δ ole:hyg no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S14. Agarose gel (0.8 %) electrophoresis of PCR fragments of putative transconjugants (#1-#4) from conjugation assay with recipient strain *M. luteus* TrpE16Δole:hyg and *Micrococcus* sp. A1 as donor. PCR reactions on donor and recipient with the same primers were performed as controls. Primers dOleH-1 and dOleH-4 targeted against a chromosomal locus specific for the recipient were used. Predicted band size for transconjugants and TrpE16Δole:hyg is 3,449 bp, for *Micrococcus* sp. A1 no band is expected. Gel was run 30 min with 140 V. M=Marker, GeneRuler 1 kb (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) was used.

Supplementary Fig. S15. Original gel of the Fig. 6. It was cropped in order to improve the clarity and conciseness of the presentation. PFGE of total DNA of *Micrococcus* sp. A1, *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan, and *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1 (TK1) before and after of 15 kb-deletion of pLMA1 in the TK1 strain. The plug-embedded and lysed cells were electrophoresed in a CHEF DR-III apparatus. Pulse times were 1–25 s for 24 h (0.5X TBE buffer, 6 V cm⁻¹, 14 °C). M: MidRange I PFG Marker (New England Biolabs); A1: *Micrococcus* sp. A1; Trp16: *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan; TK1: *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1; TK1Δ15#13 and TK1Δ15#14: strains of *M. luteus* TrpE16Δ19560:kan pLMA1 with 15 kb-deletion in linear plasmid pLMA1.